

DIGITAL CONTENT TYPES AT THE SMITHSONIAN INSTITUTION

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Abstract – Digital content is used across the Smithsonian Institution to perform the activities that are core to the organization’s mission and essential to the strategic plan. Deploying this digital content at such scale requires two key considerations, a management strategy that understands what content has Institutional value, and a supported digital ecosystem of tools that define pathways for these assets to make this value usable and accessible throughout the lifecycle.

In 2023, The Smithsonian’s Office of Digital Transformation embarked on a project to investigate, explore, map, and categorize the Smithsonian’s digital content, through a pan-institutional lens. The project’s main purpose was to identify and define the types of digital content that describe the landscape of digital products across the Institution. The investigation also identified strengths, gaps, existing systems of support, and conversational themes outlined by digital stakeholders.

This short paper will report on the project and findings. A full project report can be found at Smithsonian Research Online [1].

Submission Type – Short Paper

Keywords – content types, assessment, strategy.

Conference Topics –Haerenga – Journey

I. PROJECT SUMMARY

At the Smithsonian Institution (SI), managing valuable digital assets is an essential component to becoming a digitally mature institution. Drawing from models in the field of digital preservation, managing and building access pathways to digital assets requires secure systems of support, funding, file format and metadata standards, and policies that define what of our content to keep, manage, and appropriately share, and for how long.

This requires a comprehensive understanding of the types of *digital content* at the Institution, building a shared set of terms to strategize content across the Institution, and address commonalities and gaps. The Smithsonian recently completed a project to identify and build a list of Content Types – a taxonomy of terms – to build out a high-level understanding of digital content at SI.

To accomplish this, the project reached out to stakeholders across SI from June to November 2023. Interviews with over 102 staff members were conducted and 38 form responses were received. Representatives from collections, conservation, research, production, web, IT, data analysis, education, exhibition design, etc. were consulted.

Speaking with stakeholders also allowed us to gather intersecting research from across the Smithsonian. We encountered over 40 reports and resources from the past 15 years, including an analysis of 10 relevant internal SI policies.

Recognizing that pathways for deploying content require tools, we also set out to map these content types to systems of support and build a list of tools in the Smithsonian's technical ecosystem.

Speaking with so many stakeholders allowed us to listen and hear themes across various sectors and ask what would make the way we deploy content to our audiences "transformative". Stakeholder input was gathered into a gap analysis and recommendations section detailed in the report.

II. WHAT IS DIGITAL CONTENT?

What do we mean by "digital content"? For this project, we defined digital content as all the digital 'stuff', that is collected, created, drafted, produced,

and aggregated as part of the Smithsonian's mission-oriented activities. Mission oriented is critical here; we use mission-driven digital content to perform the activities core to our mission: "The increase and diffusion of knowledge". We collect and we do things.

The project focused on content core to our mission activities. For example, we included conservation treatment images, but not the spreadsheets to manage this data. We included data when it is mission driven, like collection records or educational data, but not visitor data or system management data. Once digital content is intentionally determined to have lasting institutional value, it is considered a digital asset.

III. PROJECT GOALS

The project's four goals were to:

- 1) Survey stakeholders on digital content they create, encounter, and/or steward.
- 2) Build a list of content types across the Institution to better categorize and understand the groups of digital assets that have value to the Institution.
- 3) Compile a list of existing research in this area at the Smithsonian.
- 4) Start to map digital assets to systems of support.

IV. CONTENT TYPES

Content and *type* are words used in various contexts at the Institution. For our purposes, the digital content type taxonomy points to the *purpose of the content*. Content types were defined as digital content that has similar business purposes, institutional function, policies, or access needs. Although out of scope for this project, content will also have one or many forms, i.e., file types, file formats, extents, etc.

These two together - *function and form* - will identify the stewardship and access pathways for assets and highlight current gaps in systems, tools, policies, and resources.

V. A TAXONOMY

To build a taxonomy of digital content types across the Smithsonian, the type groupings are organized into overarching terms. These high-level terms can be thought of as *Spaces* of activities where digital content is managed. The Spaces and high-

level sub types are listed below but defined in detail and fully listed out in the report. In the building of a simple hierarchical structure, types have two or three levels of subtypes.

<p>Collections</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessioned Collections • Non-Accessioned Collections • Collections Care <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collection Records • Conservation Documentation 	<p>Research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary Data • Derived Data Sets • Published Data Sets • Published Research • Database driven online research • Process tools and documentation
<p>Interpretive & Scholarly Material</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming/Events • Educational Content • Exhibitions • Publications 	<p>Communications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web • Social • Marketing • Advancement • Press
<p>Metadata/Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility Data • Bibliographic Data • IDs & Authorities • Rights Info • Taxonomies • Linked open data (structured) • Multilingual and translated text 	<p>Institutional Records</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Admin Records • Correspondence • HR records • Workflow/Policy Documents

Chart lists top level types or 'Spaces' and only the first level of terms in the hierarchy.

This model allows for any staff member at SI to perform work and be responsible for one or more digital content types that are outside their 'traditional' job title. For example, an Educator may create various sub types of Education material in the Interpretive Space but also create Social Media and Press Releases in the Communications Space. This way, we can attempt to expand the idea of our digital work and consider the *intention of the products* themselves as outside of our positions in the organizational structure. From there, we can build standard access pathways to fulfill the needs of our communities.

VI. SYSTEMS OF SUPPORT

Systems are crucial to supporting the pathways, stewardship, and use of digital content at scale at the Smithsonian, identifying *what files go where* and how they move through the Institution's technical system ecosystem. Since many of the tools support files across the Spaces, system support is often tied to file types (form). The project created a System Diagram [3] to convey the broader ecosystem of technological tools. Its aim was to identify all of SI's systems that support mission driven digital content, put them all on one page and slice them by purpose and use. The diagram is color coded to identify enterprise-wide supported tools, enterprise ready tools that need to be bolstered and integrated to perform more effectively, and system gaps.

VII. OTHER PROJECT DISCOVERIES

A. Institutional Ownership Statuses

Speaking with stakeholders illuminated not only six Spaces and hierarchical types, but also four ownership statuses that our digital content inhabit. These include SI Content, Non-SI materials, SI Shared Internally (among units), and SI Shared with External Partners. These statuses have their own needs in terms of stewardship, policy, and access.

B. Roles

After speaking with stakeholders about the digital content they work with, it became apparent that the lens provided is dependent on a small set of roles. From these roles stem differing but consistent challenges and priorities. Content Creators output digital content products, whether through production or documentation processes. Content Stewards manage collected or produced works and provide access to these as appropriate. Content Users are consumers and distributors of SI content for various purposes. Stakeholders can have multiple roles, and they often do across positions. However, stakeholder conversations uncovered shared concerns aligned to these separate roles.

C. Communities of Practice

Through the many conversations, one main theme was the strength of communities of practice that have developed to capitalize on the great scale of the Smithsonian. Although largely informal, there are examples where communities were formed in these Spaces to discuss challenges in stewardship,

production, and access. Communities can articulate their shared needs, target systems required to fill gaps, create content standards, and build workflow guidelines. Training community leaders to strengthen these spaces would lead to better stewardship practices, more efficient workflows, and increased value and return on the labor invested in doing the work of building and maintaining digital content pathways.

D. Policies (Directives)

Internal Smithsonian-wide policies, known as Smithsonian Directives (SDs) provide policy guidance, compliance, and enforcement mechanisms, as well as funding and resources to do the work. This project identified and analyzed ten relevant SDs and examined their inconsistencies in working with digital content. We can see the maturity of digital pathways and access for Collections over the past 10 years under the direction of SD600 [4] through its myriad funding, systems investment, shared standards development, and community growth, all directly resulting from strong policies in the form of Directives, but the other "Spaces" need official guidance. A main gap identified is the place of active Research, Interpretive and Scholarly, and Communications content that is not covered under Collections SDs or yet considered to be inactive as Institutional Business Records. This project recommends revisions to existing policies that will tackle all of our digital content, not just Collections.

E. Themes towards Transformative Practices

The project report lists out 47 gap analysis items to help steer future work, but it also documents a summary of heard themes and recommendations on how to move forward in the maturation of deploying our mission driven digital content. They can be aggregated into 5 main findings.

1. Link Existing Work

First is recognizing the amazing work already happening across the Smithsonian Institution in the creation, care, and sharing of digital content. Linking and providing access points to this diverse content, with pan institutional indexes and central data models would help to highlight and link it together as "One Smithsonian" [5].

2. Central Support

Second, central stewardship advice would tackle the need for new lifecycle understandings of

digital content, especially for produced content that is in a long term 'active' stage with unit creators and yet does not have institutional pathways or support until deposited with SI-Archives. A central Digital Stewardship initiative is in the plan for implementing the current SI Strategic Plan. There is an expressed need for central content and rights shares and coordinated campaigns for produced content, in addition to more clarity across the disparate SI directives that do not tackle policy needs for the lifecycle of our collected and produced digital content.

3. *Training and Testing*

Staff members increasingly create and interact digital content daily, making digital literacy and training essential for all staff to use and manage content. Basic records management training for digital content is crucial. Sandboxes and playgrounds to test and experiment with new tech would increase innovation and collaboration.

4. *Socializing*

Resourcing community building and shared practices among practitioners across SI leads to a shared articulation of needs and tools, as successfully modeled with staff in groups like education and social media across SI. Understanding our shared roles in relation to digital content and the ownership status of our content is crucial.

5. *Building Pathways*

Finally, building pathways for digital content requires resources, systems, and tools. Bolstering tools and defining systems of record would assist with clear Institutionally supported pathways, in addition to targeting technology ecosystem gaps.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This report was built to answer the question, *what digital content do we have?* for SI's Office of Digital Transformation, but it offers a framework and approach that could be helpful to the larger digital preservation and stewardship fields. The project was supported by stakeholders and leadership across SI through our shared desire to deploy our digital content in easier, faster, smarter, and more creative ways and to be more efficient in determining what content has long term Institutional value.

The report makes a case that the work invested in digital stewardship builds the foundation for public accessibility of our digital content. Ultimately the Institutional value of digital content is tied to its

use and reuse potential and its power to enrich the material already deemed valuable, which requires an understanding of end user audiences and SI priorities.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Smithsonian Digital Content Types". Smithsonian Research Online. 2024. <https://repository.si.edu/handle/10088/120805>
- [2] Smithsonian Mission & Strategic Plan. <https://www.si.edu/about/mission>
- [3] Digital Content Types System Diagram <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVND6gpL0=/>
- [4] Smithsonian Directive 600: Collections Management <https://www.si.edu/sites/default/files/about/sd600.pdf>
- [5] One Smithsonian is a Smithsonian initiative to bring together content from 22 museums, research centers, and the Zoo outlined in the previous Strategic Plan, 2017-22. <https://www.si.edu/strategicplan-2022/goal1>

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

This project was completed by Crystal Sanchez (OCIO, DPLAT, CDAP, DAMS), while on detail with the Office of Digital Transformation from June 2023 to March 2024, to provide an overview of the current landscape of digital content at the Smithsonian Institution and synthesize conversations with staff who work with digital content.

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